

CIM THE APPLICATION OF CITY INFORMATION MODELLING

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Abstract

Cities are becoming substantially appealing for masses in the pursuit of a better life which is spurring a large influx of population into cities. The provision of contemporary city planning, management, and monitoring mechanisms are insufficient to underpin sustainable urban development and this situation is getting exacerbated due to climate change. Many tools and strategies have been propounded in the bid to push cities towards sustainable urban development. The United Nations has presented a strategy for sustainable urban development in cities under the sustainable development goal 11 (SDG 11). Other organizations such as LEED proffer their city sustainability rating system aligned with SDG 11 to evaluate and demonstrate the sustainability performance of a city. City Information Modelling (CIM) is also developed to effectively manage a city and support evidence-based decision-making. It involves information-enriched 3D modelling of a city that is capable of facilitating the effective involvement of stakeholders due to its visualization aspects and capacity of performing analysis such as solar energy potential, noise pollution mapping, etc. CIM has been explored and implemented by many cities around the world. However, sustainability-based investigation of CIM applications is still limited in research especially the evaluation of LEED parameters with the application of CIM. This thesis focuses on conducting a state-of-art detailed assessment of sustainability parameters of LEED aligned with the capabilities of CIM to explore how CIM application can facilitate to evaluate, manifest, and accelerate sustainable urban development. A taxonomy has been proposed for 3D city modelling based on data collection and modelling approach i.e., static 3D city modelling and dynamic 3D city modelling. LEED sustainability parameters have been identified and distinguished based on the proposed taxonomy which incorporates the city elements and components to be considered for sustainability assessments. Furthermore, a framework has been propounded to develop the digital twin of a city built on the CIM structure.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-HashirUsman-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/N4zHB68U_eE

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